

INFLUENCE OF ALCOHOL ON SEXUAL EXPERIENCE AMONG WOMEN: A QUALITATIVE ANALYSIS

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Abstract

The total of seventeen in-depth interviews were conducted in this study aimed at determining the influence of alcohol on sexual experience among women. Participants were selected utilizing snowball sampling technique. Content analysis was used in analysing data with NVivo software with the aim of generating themes. Outcome of the qualitative analysis revealed that alcohol influences sexual experience among women positively and negatively. The positive influence include; increased sexual desire (alcohol serves as a trigger for some participants as it increases sexual desire, drive and mood), longer sexual acts (alcohol makes sexual act, and pleasure last longer, it gives unique sexual feeling, extra energy and improves enjoyment), and improves orgasmic experience (orgasm is achieved faster under the influence of alcohol and it comes with unique fun). While the negative influence include; delay of orgasm (it delays achieving orgasm), and the negative influence on sexual participation and involvement (engaging in sexual activity under the influence of alcohol reduces involvement and active participation, also alcohol influences the consciousness of women during sexual relation). Considering the negative and positive influence of alcohol on sexual experience, and the health-related complications associated with alcohol use among women, women should use alcohol with caution.

Keyword: Alcohol, Sexual, Experience, Women, Qualitative

INTRODUCTION

Sexual relationship generally, is a source of enjoyment and pleasure among humans when the sexual response cycle is successfully completed. Masters and Johnson (1966) reported that the human sexual response cycle is similar for males and females which has four stages of the cycle; excitement stage, plateau stage, orgasm stage and resolution stage. In contrast, Kaplan (1979) proposed a triphasic cycle of human sexual response cycle: desire, excitement and orgasm. Any stage of the sexual response cycle that is not successfully completed can result in sexual dysfunction. American Psychiatric Association (APA) (2013) classified sexual dysfunctions as; delayed ejaculation, erectile disorder, male hypoactive sexual desire disorder, premature (early) ejaculation, which are male-specific sexual dysfunctions, while female orgasmic disorder, female sexual interest/arousal disorder, genito-pelvic pain/penetration disorder, are female-specific sexual dysfunctions. Other forms of sexual dysfunctions are substance/medication induced sexual dysfunction, unspecified sexual dysfunction and other specified sexual dysfunction. Moyo (2004) reported that sexually, in patriarchal societies, women see themselves as sexual objects in positions of service to men with limited decision in terms of sexual relationship. Generally, the way sex is viewed among women affects their sexual relationship negatively, especially in relation to sexual interest, desire, involvement, participation and orgasmic experience. According to Powers (2012) achieving orgasm through intercourse is one of the most exciting aspects of many women's lives. Throughout their lifetime, about 10% of women do not experience orgasm (APA, 2013).

Among Nigerian women, Shittu et al., (2017) reported that 92% had problems related to orgasm. While Anzaku, et al., (2016) reported that in Jos Nigeria, a majority of the women studied had low arousal, sexual desire, orgasm and sexual satisfaction disorders respectively. According to Rellini, and Clifton, (2011) female orgasmic disorder relates to alcohol use. Mirone, et al., (2004) reported that delay in orgasm is affected by a small dose of alcohol. Alcohol consumption prior to recent sexual encounters is found to decrease sexual satisfaction among women (Nelson, 2013). Blum (2015) states that most women that drink alcohol, drink to enable them to fantasize and feel aroused. Globally, alcohol is the most widely used and abused substance (Karuri, 2019). Alcohol consumption in Nigeria has a long history (Ibanga, et al., 2005). Drinking alcohol can make achieving orgasm last longer or feel less intense (Fordyce, & Pathak, 2021). According to Medical Professionals of the

International Society for Sexual Medicine Communication Committee (2022a) drinking too much alcohol among men and women reduces sensation during sex and potentially make it difficult to reach orgasm. Thus, loss of sexual appetite and impotence in both men and women is explained by the fact that alcohol lowers levels of testosterone in the blood (Karuri, 2019).

In a clinical-based cross-sectional study conducted among women in Nairobi, alcohol intake is found to have significant association with female sexual disorder (Butt, et al., 2019). According to DeSantis (2020) the use of alcohol among females can lead to lack of ability to reach sexual climax. In contrast, to outcome of some studies, in a case study among 40 pregnant women in Jos South Local Government Area of Plateau State, Nigeria, pregnant women that do not drink alcohol had higher prevalence rate (42.5%) of sexual dysfunction than those that drink with prevalence rate of 27.5% (Karuri, et al., 2020). Similarly, in relation to alcohol use, significant differences in sexual function were not found between non-drinking and drinking respondents. However, among young people, sexual function is better among those that use alcohol frequently compared to those who do not (Roman, et al., 2022). Patthak (2021) reported that drinking alcohol can make achieving orgasm last longer or feel less intense. Among women dependent on alcohol, high risk of low sexual desire, female sexual dysfunction, difficulty reaching orgasm, and unsatisfied orgasm is found (Medical Professionals of the International Society for Sexual Medicine Communication Committee, 2022). During sex, women that drink alcohol hardly get aroused or reach orgasm, they have less intense orgasm and it take longer time to reach climax (Jain, 2022). Outcome of a systematic review and meta-analysis revealed that alcohol consumption among women increases the likelihood of sexual dysfunction by 74%, consumption of alcohol and increased risk of sexual dysfunction in women had significant correlation (Salari, et al., 2023).

Alcohol has a long-standing link with sexuality, drinking alcohol increases subjective sexual arousal (George, et al., 2024). Among women alcohol consumption correlates with likelihood of increased sexual dysfunction (Salari et al., 2023). In a systematic review negative relationship between consumption of alcohol and sexual function among women was found. Also, seven articles out of the 16 articles reviewed reported positive relationship between alcohol use and sexual function while 2 articles did not find any relationship between alcohol use and sexual function among women. Furthermore, increased consumption of alcohol has positive relationship with scores of female sexual function index, mild

consumption of alcohol has positive association with improved sexual function. While alcohol in excess relates to worsening sexual function and affects women's sexual desire, lubrication, arousal, satisfaction, orgasm and pain (Islam, et al., 2024).

Statement of the problem

The inability of most women to achieve a successful sexual relationship makes them die in silence. However, there are different reasons why women may not achieve a successful sexual relationship, these reasons differ based on individual differences and or personal experiences. For example, in relation to sexual dysfunction, Mahmud (2008); Diehl, et al., (2013); APA (2013); Blum, 2015); and Owojuyigbe, et al., (2017) discovered that factors such as religious norms and gender roles, religion, female genital mutilation, male dominance, and alcohol affects sexual experience. Furthermore, new view of women's sexual function discovered that, sociocultural, political or economic factors (such as anxiety and ignorance attributed to inadequate sex education, absence of care, sexual discomfort due to an individual's difficulty in meeting cultural norms regarding sexuality, lack of interest, fatigue, work related stress), psychological factors (such as, lack of trust, embarrassing sexual pleasure and sexual inhibition due to fear of sexual intercourse), partner and relationship factors (such as the fear of intimate partner abuse, traumatic experience, dislike, poor communication, when partner's opinion differ in relation to sexual desire and activity, ignorance in relation to initiation of sexual activities, loss of sexual interest, financial issues) and medical factors (such as, medical conditions that affect the circulatory, endocrine, neurological, and neurovascular system, sexual transmitter disease, pregnancy) (Tiefer, et al., 2002; Mitchell, 2008).

Based on biological theory, substance abuse and medications affect sexual functioning. Sexual interest is enhanced with alcohol in small quantities, while sexual responsiveness is depressed with excessive alcohol drinking (Halgin & Whitbourne, 2000). Even though different reasons have been identified as factors that influence women's sexual experience, in this study the researchers are interested in understanding how alcohol influences sexual experience among women. How sexually active women desire sexual satisfaction and fulfilment differ, the desire to achieve sexual fulfilment has made many sexually active women explore different ways of getting sexual satisfaction and fulfilment. Therefore, this study intends to determine whether alcohol influences sexual experience

among women or not. Thus, this study is aimed at determining the influence of alcohol on sexual experience among women.

Research Question

1. Does alcohol influence women's sexual experience?

METHOD

Research Design

This study adopted a qualitative approach utilizing in-depth interviews. The in-depth interview was conducted among heterosexual women within the Plateau North Senatorial zone; data collection stopped at the point of data saturation after conducting seventeen interviews. Participants that participated in this study were recruited utilizing snowball sampling techniques.

Participants

Four of the seventeen women that participated in this study were 22 years old, also, four were 30 years old, two were 25 years old while 21 years, 23 years, 24 years, 32 years, 33 years, 37 years, and 39 years had one participant each. Only women of the Christian faith residing within the Plateau North Senatorial zone participated in this study.

Ethical Consideration

Considering the sensitive nature of the study and the standard for best practice in human research, appropriate ethical approval was obtained from the Chairmen of the respective local government areas (Barkin Ladi, Bassa, Jos-East, Jos-North, Jos-South, and Riyom) selected for the study within Plateau North Senatorial Zone. The study was conducted according to the approved protocols and relevant institutional guidelines for conducting research with human participants. Participation was voluntary, informed consent was obtained from participants individually, all participants were informed the purpose of the study, their confidentiality and privacy were respected and ensured.

Procedure

Three research assistants (two clinical psychologists on training and one psychologist) were recruited and trained for data collection. Only sexually active heterosexual women that drink alcohol participated in the study. The in-depth interview is a semi-structured interview with one key question. Five of the interviews were conducted via telephone interview while the remaining 13 interviews were conducted physically with each of the participants separately. Each participant consent that the interview should be recorded, all data generated were transcribed, coded and subsequently analysed with NVivo computer software version 10. Data collection for the in-depth interview ended at the point of data saturation after 17 in-depth interviews were conducted.

Method of data analysis

Content analysis was used in analysing data to determine themes. All data were analysed with version 10 of NVivo software.

RESULTS

Research Question

Does alcohol influence women's sexual experience?

Code

"Alcohol has affected me because sometimes when you take alcohol you feel honey and you want to have sexual intercourse but then I think alcohol triggers the sexual desire and the fact that you would want to"

"Oaky, I think sometimes it triggers the fact that you want to do it and your body is involve you are conscious of everything that is happening"

"Because when I'm not really on alcohol, I might not really get the feeling"

"Alcohol helps me a lot in my sexual relationship with my partner because if I don't take alcohol the influence or the libido wouldn't just be there for me at all"

"Sometimes alcohol gives me sexual urge"

"Alcohol, most of the time I don't like drinking alcohol but whenever I drink alcohol it gives me more sexual desire"

"Alcohol helps me to just bring out everything just be myself without pretense or anything"

"I discover that any time we drink we stay long if we are making love and the fun is somehow unique"

“It makes me to reach orgasm quickly, which is the fun part of it. I like it like that”

“Alcohol actually affects my orgasm”

“Fast like it can come faster when I take alcohol”

“Okay, like I said before, if I have to attend this orgasm, I must not be too drunk”

“When I take alcohol at least I will give him to the best of my satisfaction. But if there's no alcohol there's nothing there.”

“Hmm! Well, you know when you are on alcohol there is this extra strength in you these vibes that you want to do things, anything you do you just enjoy it”

“To me I think a positive impact because I don't think the things, I did to reach my orgasm when I was drunk, I would be able to do them when I am normal”

“It helps me also to feel relief in the sexual aspect”

“Because when I take alcohol, it makes me feel better when I'm with my partner”

“I reach orgasm, but I don't reach it like when I take alcohol”

“Like I said it makes me feel like making out”

“Yes, because the positive is maybe when you want to do any sexual intercourse with someone you really want to do it, when you are drunk you enjoy it”

“However, at times when I drink alcohol the sexual feeling is better for me compared to when I don't drink”

“Like when I'm tipsy I might love to go wild, having sex you do things that after everything you will be asking yourself like where did I get that concept from?”

“To reach... yeah there is delay, it delays first but after that at the end of everything you will still reach the orgasm”

“It's only when I am so excited and just myself like I said during ovulation I think it helps a lot but ordinarily like that I hardly reach orgasm when I am normal”

“Sometimes it delays and sometimes it comes”

“Sometimes it delays in the sense that we will have it like one, two times before it comes”

“Okay, well the negative impact is I won't participate”

“If I take it, I don't really know what happens around”

“The thing is that when I’m drunk my husband used to say I do... I do... I do well... well, but me I don’t usually know what happens”

“Actually, alcohol delays my orgasm”

“For me negative oh!”

“Because if I do, I don’t even use to know that I do because I don’t even use to know if I am enjoying it or I’m not enjoying it”

“When I drink alcohol, it delays my orgasm, because the alcohol makes me last longer before achieving orgasm”

Alcohol Use Patterns and Female Orgasmic Disorder

Findings of the study revealed positive and negative influence of alcohol on orgasmic experience. The positive influence of alcohol on women’s orgasmic experience are; increased sexual desire, longer sexual acts, and improves orgasmic experience. The negative influence of alcohol on orgasmic experience are; delay of orgasm, and the negative influence on sexual participation and involvement.

Themes

Positive influence of alcohol on women’s sexual experience

Increased sexual desire

Common responses of participants showed that alcohol increased and enhanced sexual desire as it serves as a trigger for some participants. Sexual drive, desire or mood is a key factor in determining an enjoyable sexual experience, which also increases the likelihood of achieving satisfactory orgasmic experience. Statements such as *“Alcohol helps me a lot in my sexual relationship with my partner because if I don’t take alcohol the influence or the libido wouldn’t just be there for me at all”* and *“So, alcohol has affected me because sometimes when you take alcohol you feel honey and you want to have sexual intercourse but then I think alcohol triggers the sexual desire and the fact that you would want to”* this responses point to the fact that alcohol influence and triggers sexual desire and drive and it also enhances sexual drive. Furthermore, common statements such as *“I think sometimes alcohol triggers the fact that you want to have sex and your body is involve, also you are conscious of everything that is happening”*, this statement by a participant shows how the participant makes conscious effort for sexual activities due to the influence of alcohol in

relation to the desires and drives that alcohol provides in relation to sexual activity. This statement *“However, at times when I drink alcohol the sexual feelings are better for me compared to when I don’t drink”* shows that comparing the influence of alcohol on sexual desires when one is sober and under the influence of alcohol, the sexual desire is more exciting for some participants.

Longer sexual acts

Participants' responses also showed that some common responses by participants indicate that alcohol makes sexual activity last longer, which also makes sexual pleasure last longer and further enhances orgasmic experience. This statement, *“I discover that any time we drink we stay long if we are making love and the fun is somehow unique”*, and the statement *“Hmm! Well, you know when you are on alcohol there is this extra strength in you, this vibe that you want to do things, anything you do you just enjoy it”*. The aforementioned statements showed that alcohol gives a unique sexual feeling, enjoyment, extra energy and makes the sexual act last longer.

Improves orgasmic experience

Common statements revealed that alcohol enhances orgasmic experience for some participants. The following statements point to this *“It makes me to reach orgasm quickly which is the fun part of it. I like it like that”* and *“Fast like it can come faster when I take alcohol”*. Furthermore, common statements such as *“I reach orgasm, but I don’t reach it like when I take alcohol”* show the importance that participants place on alcohol in enhancing orgasmic experience. Alcohol makes achieving orgasm faster and it comes with unique fun.

Negative influence of alcohol on women’s sexual experience

Delay of orgasm

Outcome of the study based on responses by some participants indicates that alcohol delays orgasm among some participants which indicates the negative effect of alcohol on women’s orgasmic experience. The following statement, *“Actually, alcohol delays my orgasm”*, and *“When I drink alcohol, it delays my orgasm”*. *“Okay, sometimes it delays in the sense that we will have it like one, two times before it comes”* provides details on how alcohol delays orgasm among some participants when they engage in sexual relation under the influence of alcohol.

Negative influence on sexual participation and involvement

Responses further indicate that among some of the participants alcohol reduces involvement and active participation in sexual activities. Participants' responses such as;

“Okay, well the negative impact is I won’t participate”, and “The thing is that when I’m drunk my husband used to say I do... I do... I do well... well, but I don’t usually know what happens”. This shows that alcohol influences the consciousness of women during sexual activities. This points to inactive involvement and participation in sexual activity which in turn means not experiencing orgasm; as some factors that could influence and enhance orgasm such as desire, interest and enjoyment are absent. The statement, *“because if I do, I don’t even use to know that I do because I don’t even use to know if I am enjoying it or I’m not enjoying it”* points to this fact.

DISCUSSION

Findings of this study aimed at determining the influence of alcohol on sexual experience among women reveal both negative and positive influence of alcohol on women’s sexual experience. McCool-Meyers et al., (2018) had reported that the effect of alcohol consumption is unclear in relation to female sexual dysfunction. In this present study it was discovered that negatively, alcohol delays women’s orgasmic experience. Participants indicate how alcohol delays them from achieving orgasm during sexual intercourse. Similarly, Wincze (2009) reported that alcoholic women may have problems having orgasm. Inhibited orgasm is reported among heavy drinking women (Johnson et al., 2004). Witting (2008) discovered that women who drink alcohol prior to sexual intercourse have more problems with orgasm. Alcohol in small quantities delays orgasm (Mirone et al., 2004). Also, alcohol negatively influences some participants’ sexual participation and involvement during sexual intercourse. Sexual relationship under the influence of alcohol affects the women’s consciousness which makes them not to be fully aware of their participation and involvement during sexual acts with their partner. Not actively participating in the sexual relationship affects orgasm considering that factors such as enjoyment, desire and interest are absent during sexual relationships due to the influence of alcohol. According to Medical Professionals of the International Society for Sexual Medicine Communication Committee (2022) drinking too much alcohol among men and women reduces sensation during sex and potentially makes it difficult to reach orgasm. During sex, women that drink alcohol hardly get aroused or reach orgasm, they have less intense orgasm and it takes longer time to reach climax (Jain, 2022).

The positive influence of alcohol on women’s orgasmic experience based on participants common responses are, increased sexual desire, longer sexual acts and improve

orgasmic experience. Sexual intercourse under the influence of alcohol enhances sexual desire which serves as a trigger among some of the participants. Importantly, achieving an enjoyable sexual experience requires adequate sexual desire, drive and or mood, also, these factors serve as important factors that likely increase a satisfactory orgasm. For some participants they make conscious effort during sexual relationships under the influence of alcohol as it enhances their sexual desire and interest. Similarly, Kling, et al., (2019) discovered that hazardous alcohol drinking among women makes sexual function better. Also, Blum (2015) discovered that most women that drink alcohol, drink in order to enhance their sexual arousal. Similarly, common responses in this present study showed that sexual feelings under the influence of alcohol for some women is better compared to when they are not under the influence of alcohol. Furthermore, alcohol boosts sexual energy, makes sexual relationships and sexual pleasure last longer. This implies that drinking alcohol deliberately by some women prior to sexual relationship makes the feelings associated with the sexual relationship unique and enjoyable and makes the sexual relationship last longer. For some women alcohol improves their orgasmic experience, this indicates the importance of alcohol in improving women's orgasm especially the unique fun derived during sexual relationship under the influence of alcohol and how it makes orgasm faster. In contrast, Patthak (2021) discovered that achieving orgasm under the influence of alcohol can be less intense, last longer or delayed. George, et al., (2011) discovered that higher levels of drinking alcohol reduces sexual drive while lower levels of drinking improve sexual drives. Sexual interest is enhanced with alcohol in small quantities, while sexual responsiveness is depressed with excessive alcohol drinking (Halgin & Whitbourne, 2000).

While alcohol enhances sexual desire, interest, drive and performance among some women, for others alcohol dulls their conscience and delays their orgasm. Thus, for women that alcohol dulls their conscience, even if alcohol negatively influences their sexual experience they may not know since they are not fully aware of what happens during the sexual experience considering that alcohol dulls their conscience. However, some women drink alcohol prior to sexual intercourse for no specific reason. This implies that the reason why women use alcohol in relation to sexual relationships and how alcohol influences women's sexual experience differs. Despite the outcome of this study, this study is not without limitations. The inability of the study to identify the specific brand of alcohol that influences women's sexual experience could it be the locally brewed or refined?

Conclusion

It is concluded in this study that alcohol has a dual (negative and positive) influence on sexual experience among women. The following themes were discovered: alcohol increases sexual desire, makes sexual intercourse last longer, improves orgasmic experience. And negatively, alcohol delays orgasm, and negatively influences active sexual participation and involvement. However, irrespective of the positive effect of alcohol on women's sexual experience, women should note the health-related effects and complications associated with alcohol use as reported by Erol & Karpyak (2015); WHO, (2024) and Women's' Recovery (2024), the authors reported several health-related complications associated with alcohol drinking among women. These include, higher blood level compared to men, more susceptible to long-term negative consequences, pregnancy related complications and birth defects, behavioural problems such as depression and anxiety, mental health condition, liver and heart disease, dehydration, stroke, decreased fertility and sexual dysfunction. Thus, considering the negative and positive influence of alcohol on sexual experience, and the health-related complications associated with alcohol use among women, women should use alcohol with caution.

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